

THE ART OF COMMUNICATION BETWEEN A MEDICAL PROFESSIONAL AND A PATIENT

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Abstract. *This article is devoted to the study of a relevant issue in clinical medicine – medical ethics and deontology. It presents a modern understanding of the fundamentals of medical ethics and deontology. Medical ethics and deontology are essential components of the work of healthcare professionals. Various aspects of the topic are considered, highlighting the multifaceted nature and complexity of forming the professional personality of a medical worker.*

Keywords: *ethics, deontology, medical professionals, ethical and moral norms.*

Introduction

Medicine possesses a long-standing experience in caring for sick individuals, which has certain specific characteristics distinguishing it from other professional activities. Medicine is guided by ethical and moral norms, which are influenced by the economic and socio-political context. The term “ethics” was first introduced by Aristotle, who understood it as the science of human morality.

Deontology (from Greek deontos – duty) is the study of proper behavior and actions. In other words, it is a set of ethical rules, norms, and principles that a medical professional must follow. It is important to remember that “doctors are not born, they become doctors”. The formation of a physician requires three components: first, medical knowledge; second, the practical application of this knowledge, i.e., mastery of medical procedures and actions; and third, the physician must have a distinctive character (selflessness), a high sense of responsibility for their actions, a style of thinking and behavior based on moral and ethical norms, and qualities of empathy toward patients.

The term “ethics” was first proposed by Aristotle as the science of human morality. The term “deontology” originates from Greek, where deon means “duty” and logos – “study”. This term was introduced by the English philosopher J. Bentham in the 19th century to denote the science of professional human conduct.

Aim, Objectives, Materials, and Methods

The aim of this work is to study the current state of medical ethics and deontology through the method of analytical review of scientific literature.

Research Results

Medical ethics and deontology is a science that substantiates the principles of behavior for medical personnel, aimed at creating the necessary conditions during examination, treatment, and rehabilitation of patients. It considers not only conditions that promote the effectiveness of treatment but also measures that prevent negative outcomes. In this context, it refers to the proper conduct of all medical personnel in the interest of protecting human health.

Physician deontology, taking into account all social, psychological, and professional aspects, includes several areas related to interpersonal relationships, each of which requires careful study and reflection:

1. Physician and patient – moral aspects of interaction and communication.
2. Physician and patient’s environment, including close relatives, friends, colleagues, and others.
3. Physician and society, including the state, law, and legal framework.
4. Physician and colleagues, i.e., interactions within the medical team and among medical staff.
5. Physician and self, including self-assessment, evaluation of successes or mistakes, and self-control.

Deontology in medical practice must encompass all five areas. At the same time, the moral character of the physician, their professionalism, broad knowledge, and ability to conduct conversations tactfully—convincing patients regarding health or illness-related issues—are especially critical in the “Physician and patient(s)” aspect.

Medical ethics and deontology are primarily based on high medical morality. The central elements of medical ethics and deontology include the relationship between medical personnel and patients, high professionalism, and interpersonal relations among medical staff. As a subject, physician deontology can also utilize standards. For example, professional and ethical qualities of a physician, especially in promoting a healthy lifestyle (HLS) among the population, can be defined as specific standards:

- Education, including medical knowledge
- Mastery of all HLS-promoting skills
- Ability to clearly express thoughts and analyze situations
- Kindness
- Correctness (tactfulness)

Undoubtedly, all the listed standards (criteria) for a good physician should also encompass the other areas of deontology. Ethical and deontological convictions and the moral character of a medical professional in everyday practice are expressed primarily through communication with patients, their relatives, colleagues, and coworkers; the physician’s authority in society also plays an important role. Problems of communication represent a complex, multifaceted process of establishing contact between people, which includes the exchange of information, perception and understanding of one another, and often the evaluation of another person. Communication is an important psychological category with its own interdependencies.

In deontology, a significant psychological and pedagogical aspect is the physician’s behavior. Intelligence, a sense of tact, the ability to listen, and the ability to guide a patient’s thoughts in the appropriate direction—these and other positive qualities should be inherent in modern physicians. In any form of communication, much depends on the culture and moral character of individuals: some people are polite and strive to understand and help others, while others are rude, tactless, seek to dismiss the interlocutor, treat them disrespectfully, and sometimes even offensively. Communication techniques are important: the ability to initiate and establish contact, understand and build relationships, and penetrate the inner world of another person.

Various means of the communicative process are known—gestures, facial expressions, intonation, and others; however, the most important is the physician’s speech. The dialogue between physician and patient should proceed within the framework of benevolence and sincere mutual interest and should be aimed at achieving a common goal the preservation and strengthening of health.

The physician's primary task is to maintain hope, as it is the foremost condition for recovery. The ancients said that "it is not so much examination as attentive care that a patient needs." A patient needs to be listened to; they want to believe that the physician cares whether they live or die and to be confident that the physician is concerned about their health. Through the physician's behavior—even by the mere fact of their presence—the physician can create conditions either for recovery or, conversely, for the deterioration of the patient's condition. No modern methods or the latest equipment can replace the physician as a healer.

Thus, the art of the physician lies in the ability to develop a proper attitude toward individual people both toward the patient and toward the patient's relatives. An important element in deontological practice is the physician's speech (the words spoken during conversation with the patient). A physician's speech should not only be expressive but should also convey the necessary information. At the same time, speech and voice should be harmonious, dignified, and pleasant. One should not speak to a patient too loudly, noisily, hastily, rapidly, or in a грубым (harsh) tone.

Medical Confidentiality in Deontological Practice

Medical confidentiality in deontological practice originates from deep antiquity and is defined in the Hippocratic Oath as one of the leading elements of a physician's professional activity. Medical confidentiality refers to information about a patient's illness, as well as their personal and intimate life, which becomes known to medical professionals in the course of performing their professional duties. For a long time, the preservation of medical confidentiality was regarded solely as a moral norm and an ethical obligation of a medical worker.

Conclusion

By concluding it should be suggested that an important aspect for a physician is the continuous improvement of their lifestyle. In this regard, from the very beginning of professional activity, a physician must learn to value time and plan it effectively. A physician devotes time every day to self-improvement, studies new developments in their specialty, and continuously works with scientific literature, including online resources. A physician must also remain constantly informed about political, social, and economic events, both domestically and internationally.

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